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Development of common
procedures and tools

Workpackage 2.1

Responsible Partner: RIVM

Contributing partners: All COHESIVE
partenrs

GENERAL INFORMATION

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Approach

Within COHESIVE guidelines are developed to support countries to set up national One Health systems (such as present in for instance The Netherlands and UK) or other ways to strengthen human-veterinary collaborations. The aim is to improve signalling, risk assessment and response by better communication, (early) exchange of information, sharing of knowledge and joint forces. This is important for (re)emerging pathogens, but also the response to notifiable pathogens will profit from better collaboration. Since countries are very different in many aspects, no blueprint can be made for such One Health systems. In an integrated approach web-based guidelines were developed with the title 'One Health: Setting up a risk analysis system for zoonoses'. The URLs are <http://www.ohras.eu> and www.onehealthguidelines.eu. Due to administrative issues the link are not available yet. To get there, a co-creative process was followed. This started with a needs assessment consisting of workshops, focus groups, questionnaires, and interviews. The main conclusion was that there is a need for such guidelines which should focus on operation and implementation. Key principles such as respect, trust and responsibility are considered important as they can drive behaviour, decision-making, collaboration, and governance processes in relation to setting up a One Health Risk Analysis System (OHRAS)(see poster). In the first two years a lot of (physical) workshops were organised, gathering information. This was a highly effective approach, which was disturbed by COVID. After postponing physical workshops a couple of times, at a certain moment it was concluded that physical meetings were no longer an option and virtual workshops were organised instead.

An overview of the global activities are indicated below. Minutes of dedicated workshops and a poster are added. For promotion purposes 3 leaflets were developed explaining the WHY, WHAT and HOW of the guidelines. Those are attached as well.

Workshop at APHA, 26-27 November 2018

Workshop at annual meeting at SVA, 10-12 April 2019

Interviews 2019

Workshop at Sciensano, 1-2 July 2019

Workshop at APHA, 8-9 October 2019

Workshop at general meeting at SSI, 27-29 November 2019

Six virtual workshops, 2020-2021

Workshop at end symposium, 8-10 November 2021

Guidelines

The guideline consists of five steppingstones that countries can follow to set up or improve the human-veterinary-food-environment collaboration in the area of risk analysis of zoonoses, namely **set priority and goal, stakeholder analysis, systems mapping of the current situation, designing a OHRAS, implementing a OHRAS**. For designing and implementing a OHRAS, information is given on six essential One Health activities namely **OH Signalling, OH Risk Assessment, OH Feasibility Assessment, OH risk Management, OH Coordinated Communication and OH Governance**. The guideline is web based to facilitate easy searching of dedicated information, based on the needs of the user for instance when only wanting to implement a OH Risk Assessment team. During the needs assessment barriers hampering One

Health collaboration were identified and confirmed by another method in WP3.1. Suggestions are made on how to deal with four of them, **gaining political will, obtaining trust, sharing information and communication**. The guideline can be seen as a toolbox harboring a set of tools, such as the systems mapping workshop, an interactive tool to design a OHRAS, Terms of Reference guidance with prefilled formats. Also links to other useful tools, including tools developed in other COHESIVE workpackages. There has been close collaboration with the SISOT working group of the Tripartite FAO, OIE and WHO. There will be cross reference between the SISOT toolbox and the COHESIVE guidelines for risk analysis of zoonoses. The guidelines will become part of the SISOT toolbox. The guidelines will be linked to the MedVetNet Association (MVNA) website, to secure long-term sustainability.

Snap shots of the website

Welcome to the guideline *'One Health: Setting up a risk analysis system for zoonoses'*

WHY	Zoonoses are a constant threat to human and animal health. A systematic cross-sectoral (One Health) approach to share signals, assess risks and coordinate the response is essential to minimize impact of zoonotic diseases.	
GOAL	Support countries to set up or strengthen their collaboration in the area of risk analysis of zoonoses and AMR, in a One Health fashion. In our definition risk analysis comprises of signalling, risk assessment, risk management and risk communication.	
INTENDED FOR	Professionals who are involved in the risk analysis of zoonoses and antimicrobial resistance (AMR), who would like to make a change in the One Health collaboration, within their country. With this guideline, professionals can take the initiative themselves to set up an interdisciplinary partnership between professionals in the human and veterinary health sectors, and in other sectors, such as food safety and environmental health, and develop an (institutionalized) One Health risk analysis system (OHRAS) to deal with the prevention and control of zoonotic diseases and AMR.	
FOCUS	HOW	INCLUDED
On implementation and operationalisation	Stepwise approach to implement OHRAS allowing to tailor it to your country's situation and needs.	Addressing barriers that can be faced, such as the difficulty to obtain political will or to gain trust.
CO-CREATION		
This guideline is co-created by professionals from public health institutes, veterinary institutes and food safety authorities within COHESIVE, a One Health EJP project. It is based on their own experience with One Health risk analysis systems, and on the Tripartite Zoonoses Guide . We hope you find this a practical guide for the co-creation of a One Health risk analysis approach in your country.		

Funding About Us About this site Contact

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- Get Started
- Set Priority and Goal
- Stakeholder analysis
- Systems mapping of the current situation
- Designing a One Health risk analysis system**
- Building a One Health risk analysis system

Designing a One Health Risk Analysis System

The core of designing a One Health Risk Analysis System (OHRAS) is to identify and organise the separate activities within the system in a One Health fashion. How to proceed will depend on the existing structures, relations and actions and the specific situation in your country. When we refer to OHRAS, we also imply part of the system.

Activities of OHRAS

We have defined a complete OHRAS as a combination of the following One Health (OH) activities:

- OH Signalling
- OH Risk Assessment
- OH Feasibility Assessment
- OH Risk Management
- OH Risk Communication
- OH Governance

These activities form the building blocks of an OHRAS. The way in which these activities can be designed and implemented is very flexible and can therefore be specifically adapted and applied to the needs of each country. The prefix "One Health" refers to working with relevant sectors on the defined objective(s). The integration of knowledge and action can occur at different points of the activity. The principal idea is that, ultimately, the activities in the system are coherent and coordinated. Where in the operational process you bring people together can be determined for each activity separately. Depending on your needs, abilities, support and/or resources it is also possible to choose to start by organising only one or two of the activities in a One Health fashion. More information on the OH activities can be found under the tab "OH activities" at the top of the page.

Designing OHRAS

Get started by organising one or more meetings to brainstorm on the design of your OHRAS. Use your stakeholder analysis to help determine who to invite to these brainstorm, with the different activities in mind. Discuss and determine which parts of the risk analysis you feel are important to organise in a One Health fashion. The system map can be used to support the discussion on where collaboration is already working and where not, where joint efforts are wanted and should be improved or established. You can use the system map to visually encircle where the activities take place now, which will show whether the relevant stakeholders are already connected or not. The next question is whether you feel that connections should be implemented/improved. It is important, to build on existing infrastructures, relations and activities. You don't want to compete with the existing system by building a new one but endorse and extend what is there. Thus, step by step, the team reflects and decides on next steps for improvement towards their common vision of the OHRAS. As we mentioned earlier, this is a continuous process which requires a sustained commitment and adaptive leadership. Over time the challenges and conditions of the OHRAS will change and it will need to adapt.

To support the discussion on this design phase, an interactive tool is provided on the website. With this tool you can visualise the teams you would like to have in your OHRAS based upon the activities they are performing and at what level governance take place. An instruction for this application can be downloaded here. For the application to start, click on 'Let's build!'

[Let's Build](#)

Guidelines for risk analysis of zoonoses Home Get Started **OH Activities** More Information

OH Activities	<h3>OH Signalling Introduction</h3> <p>GOAL:</p> <p>Sharing information on events or trends at an early stage with relevant parties across sectors, facilitating the assessment of (potential) zoonotic risks in a One Health fashion.</p> <p>WHY:</p> <p>Early Signalling ensures a rapid response. Timely information sharing and joint signal evaluation across sectors decrease the response times and might also increase the efficiency of the response by steering it directly to the responsible sector.</p> <p>WHAT:</p> <p>Organise signalling in a One Health fashion by collecting signals and sharing them regularly and timely across sectors. Together make a quick evaluation of whether a certain signal poses a health threat and further actions are needed.</p> <p>The OH Signalling team that meets regularly should consist of experts from relevant organisations, ideally representing the sectors and disciplines from across One Health (public health, veterinary health, food safety and environmental health). The signals should be from the prioritised group of zoonoses that has been defined in step 1 of the implementation stepping stones. During the meetings of the OH Signalling team, a quick risk estimation of the signal should be made. Tools to support quick risk estimation can be found under Tools. If a signal is expected to be a (potential) zoonotic health threat, upscaling can be done within the OH risk analysis system (OHRAS). On the page Tips & Experiences examples from other countries can be found for inspiration, including tips on e.g. the criteria to determine when a signal should be flagged for further action.</p> <p>HOW:</p> <p>Make use of the guidance on the Terms of Reference page how to organise your OH Signalling team.</p> <p>On the Terms of Reference (ToR) page you will be guided through the different elements that can be included in the ToR of the OH Signalling team. The ToR have the same format for all teams. A form is provided to immediately shape the ToR document for later use. An important aspect for the OH Signalling team is the selection of the team. The team composition should be appropriate to the signals of interest and include experts involved in surveillance and laboratory analysis as well as response and control. Under the 'way of working', for instance, the frequency of meetings and the process of determining whether signals are potential threats and further action is needed are determined. See also Tips & Tricks for more ideas.</p>
OH Signalling	
Definition and goal	
Terms of reference	
Tips & Experiences	
Tools	
OH Risk Assessment	
OH Feasibility Assessment	
OH Risk Management	
OH Coordinated Communication	
OH Governance	

Guidelines for risk analysis of zoonoses Home Get Started OH Activities More Information [Generate PDF](#)

Back

Team

OH Signalling

OH Risk Assessment

OH Feasibility Assessment

OH Risk Management

OH Risk Communication

Governance

Clear All

- More Information
- Barriers
- Political will
- Trust
- Sharing information
- Communication
- Definition and Goals
- Terms of Reference
- Tips & Experiences
- Tools

Barrier Political will

Political will is one of the fundamental drivers for a well-functioning early warning system, such as a One Health Risk Analysis System (OHRAS). Having political will from the policy makers goes hand in hand with ensuring essential resources, funding, and infrastructure. Here, we define political will, its associated challenges and provide guidance to build political will. This is the combined result of literature and expert consultation. The experts that were consulted were One Health professionals that shared their knowledge and expertise in the topic of political will at workshops, focus groups and semi-structured interviews where a central theme of the discussions was the establishment of a OHRAS.

What is political will in the context of OHRAS?

Political theorists see 'political will' as an ambiguous concept especially when the government does not act due to a lack of political will. Over two decades ago, Hammetgren (1998) characterised political will as 'the slipperiest concept in the policy lexicon', calling it the 'sine qua non of policy success which is never defined except by its absence'. Oxford lexicon defines political will as follows: political intention or desire (in early use not as a fixed collocation); (later) specifically the firm intention or commitment on the part of a government to carry through a policy, especially one which is not immediately successful or popular. One Health professionals suggest that political will in the context of OHRAS is a firm commitment of the government to implement policies leading to functional and sustainable OHRAS.

What are the challenges of political will in the context of OHRAS?

The actual challenges of the political will may vary depending on the context, type of One Health risks and country. The most present challenges that we need to react to are:

- How to set One Health (risks) on the agenda?
- How to get the One Health sectors/institutions/professionals to join forces in building political will?
- How can you understand and influence prioritisation of your government?
- Who are the governmental officials we need to approach?
- How to communicate with government officials like policy makers?

How can you as a One Health professional build political will?

In order to build political will, One Health professionals need to work together, set a political agenda, understand the prioritisation of governmental institutions, and communicate in an effective manner. These elements are described below.

1. **Agenda-setting**: From the health policy perspective, agenda setting is the issue-sorting phase in the public policy process, during which some concerns rise to the attention of policy makers while others remain neglected. Power - who holds it and how it is exercised - is a central concern in health agenda-setting research. The most influential model of the agenda-setting process postulates that issues rise to the attention of policy makers when problems, solutions and political developments converge, creating windows of opportunity. Following this, One Health professionals can capitalise on the 'policy window' offered by recent global